

“Tumor budding effect on cutaneous head and neck squamous cell carcinoma evolution.”

Gonzalez-Guerrero M MD¹, Martínez-Cambor P MD, PhD^{2,3}, Vivanco B MD, PhD^{1,4}, Fernández-Vega I MD, PhD¹, Munguia-Calzada P MD⁶, Gonzalez-Gutierrez MP MD¹, Rodrigo JP MD, PhD⁵, Galache C MD, PhD⁶, Santos-Juanes J MD, PhD^{3,6}.

1. Department of Pathology. Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias. Oviedo. Spain.
2. Geisel School of Medicine at Dartmouth. Dartmouth College, Hannover, NH, USA.
3. Universidad Autónoma de Chile, Santiago, Chile.
4. Unit of Dermatopathology. Department of Pathology. Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias. Oviedo. Spain.
5. Department of Otolaryngology. Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias. Oviedo. Spain.
6. Service of Dermatology II. Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias. Oviedo. Spain.

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Corresponding autor.

Jorge Santos-Juanes MD,PhD.

jorgesantosjuan@gmail.com

CAPSULE SUMMARY

- Risk factors for metastasis from cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma are incorporated in tumor staging by the seventh edition of the American Joint Committee on Cancer Staging Manual.
- We confirmed most risk factors, and also identified tumor buds as a predictor for lymph node metastasis
- Tumor buds can be considered in tumor staging

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma (cSCC) is the second most common malignancy in humans. Approximately 5% metastasized, usually to regional lymph nodes. Tumor budding is a readily detectable histopathological feature and has been recognized as an adverse prognostic factor in several human cancers.

OBJECTIVE: To assess the correlation of tumor budding with the clinicopathologic features and the prognostic value of tumor budding in cSCC.

METHODS: 49 primary cSCC non-metastatic and 49 cSCC primary metastatic to regional lymph nodes were retrospectively included. Statistical analyses were carried out to assess the relationship between tumor budding, clinicopathologic parameters and patient survival.

RESULTS: Tumor budding was observed in 45 cases (46%) with a mean tumor bud count of 5.9 ± 3.9 (range from 1 to 20 buds). High-intensity budding (≥ 5 tumor buds) was observed in 20 tumors. Tumor buds has a significant risk factor for nodal metastasis with crude and adjusted hazard ratios (HR) of 8.92 (CI=4.39-18.1) and 6.93 (3.30-14.5), respectively and on the overall survival time (crude and adjusted HR of 2.03 (1.26-3.28) and 1.72 (1.05-2.83), respectively).

LIMITATIONS: The retrospective study design.

CONCLUSION: These results indicate an increased frequency of nodal metastasis and risk of death in patients with tumour buds.

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma (cSCC) is the second most common malignancy
3 in humans with an incidence of 16 per 100,000 people in Europe (1). Approximately 5% of
4 cSCC metastatize, usually to regional lymph nodes (2). Within the current Tumour Node
5 Metastasis (TNM) classification of non-melanoma skin cancers by the American Joint
6 Committee on Cancer (AJCC) and the International Union Against Cancer (UICC), the
7 primary tumour is characterized by a combination of horizontal size and “high risk factors”
8 (1). According to this staging system T1 tumours are 20 mm or less in greatest dimension
9 with fewer than two high-risk features, T2 tumours are greater than 2 cm in greatest
10 dimension with or without one additional high-risk feature, or any size with two or more
11 high-risk features, T3 tumours are with invasion of maxilla, mandible, orbit, or temporal
12 bone, and T4 are tumours with invasion of skeleton (axial or appendicular) or perineural
13 invasion of skull base. Several characteristics, such as primary site on ear or hair-bearing
14 lip, poor differentiation (high grade), thickness, anatomic level, presence of perineural
15 invasion, and presence of lymph-vascular invasion have been include as “high risk factors”
16 (1). Moreover, many other characteristics, such as inflammatory response, association with
17 actinic keratosis, association with human papillomavirus (HPV), association with Bowen’s
18 disease, and some kind of histological subtypes like acantholytic, basaloid, small cell, signet
19 ring, desmoplastic or spindle cell histological subtypes, and follicular SCC have also been
20 suggested as prognostic factors (2-6).

21 Wang et al. proposed that cancer cells located in the invasive tumor front are more
22 aggressive in terms of metastatic potential (7). Tumor budding is defined as the presence of
23 either isolated single cells or small cell clusters (up to four) scattered in the stroma ahead of
24 the invasive tumor front (8). Budding represents two malignant features: cellular
25 discohesion and active invasion. The presence of tumor buds has been considered to be a

26 characteristic of aggressive cancer. Tumor budding has previously been found as a
27 prognostic marker for colorectal cancer patients (8), lung carcinoma (9), ampullary
28 adenocarcinoma (10), laryngeal cancers (11), and tongue squamous cell carcinoma (12).

29 With the goal of studying the possible association of tumor budding and clinicopathologic
30 features and establish their potential prognostic value in cSCC, a retrospective study was
31 performed.

32 METHODS

33 Patients and procedures

34 The Department of Pathology electronic database at Hospital Universitario Central de
35 Asturias was searched to locate all the patients who had developed nodal metastases from
36 cSCC of head and neck between 1998 and 2007. Two of the authors (MG and JP) read
37 reports identified by this search. Cases of noncutaneous cSCC, cSCC in situ, and recurrent
38 cSCC were excluded as well as cSCC developing on mucosal surfaces. Also any kind of
39 histological subtype not considered as “pure cSCC”, like keratoacanthoma,
40 lymphoepitelioma-like carcinoma of the skin, collision tumours of SCC, and basal-cell
41 carcinoma (eg, cSCC located so closely to a basal-cell carcinoma that they appear as one
42 tumour). We reviewed (IF and MP) the electronic medical records to determine whether
43 outcomes of interest occurred, including local recurrence, in transit metastasis, nodal
44 metastases, and death cSCC. Finally, a total of forty-nine primary metastasizing cutaneous
45 squamous cell carcinomas (McSCC) of head and neck that had evolved to histologically
46 confirmed lymph node metastases were included. Sequentially, a control group of forty-nine
47 patients with head and neck cSCC who had not developed any metastases and with a
48 minimum follow-up of 4-year was also evaluated. All the tumors had been excised with
49 conventional surgery. None of the patients received any form of adjuvant therapy after their

50 surgery. Ethics approval was obtained from the Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias
51 Committee. The study was done and results were reported according to the STROBE
52 guidelines for case-control studies.

53 Clinical patient-related data were collected retrospectively, including date of birth, sex,
54 previous SCC, presence of immunosuppression caused by chemotherapy or malignancies
55 other than non-melanoma skin cancer and tumour site (ear, nose, cheek, scalp, pre-ear, retro-
56 ear, front, periocular, chin and temple). Patient age was defined as age at the time of
57 resection.

58 Histopathological evaluation

59 Two evaluators (GM and BV) simultaneously analyzed each sample and registered the
60 following histopathological features using hematoxylin and eosin stained slides: maximum
61 diameter, maximum tumor thickness (measured by use of an ocular micrometer), anatomic
62 level (Clark's level), histopathological degree of differentiation on a scale of good,
63 moderate, and poor, presence of desmoplasia on light microscopy (defined as fine branches
64 of tumour cells at the periphery and a surrounding stromal reaction), findings of perineural
65 or perivascular invasion, and the presence and number of tumor budding (defined as the
66 presence of either isolated single cells or small cell clusters (up to four) scattered in the
67 stroma ahead of the invasive tumor front). For each case all H&E tumor slides were assessed
68 independently by two pathologists. Median number of slides per case available for analysis
69 was 4 (range: 1 to 5 slides). Tumor specimens were initially scanned at the $\times 4$ objective lens
70 (and $\times 10$ ocular) to select the areas with the highest density of budding. Tumor budding in
71 the selected areas was then counted using the $\times 40$ objective lens, and the highest count per
72 slide was used as the number of budding. The cases were deemed either positive (≥ 1 buds
73 present) or negative (no buds present) for tumor budding. The intensity of tumor budding

74 (budding index) was classified as low (< 5 buds) or high (≥ 5 buds) based on Wang study (7).
75 There was total agreement among the two pathologist about the presence/absence of tumor
76 budding. Excellent agreement on the count of buds was obtained between both observers
77 ($\kappa=0.816$), based on a hierarchical kappa test. These cases were reevaluated using a double-
78 headed microscope and the disagreement resolved.

79

80 Pathologic tumour staging (pT1, pT2, pT3, pT4) based on the 7th AJCC classification was
81 also registered (1). Outcome data were based on one tumour per patient.

82

83 Statistical analysis

84 Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients and pathological data were
85 summarized with standard descriptive statistics. The primary endpoints were time to lymph-
86 node metastasis and time to the death, defined as the time from date of diagnosis of the
87 primary tumour to date of diagnosis of metastasis or death respectively. To identify
88 predictors for fatal outcomes, we select several features previously known to be high-risk
89 factors: tumor size (≤ 20 mm; >20 mm), tumour thickness (≤ 2.0 mm, 2.1-6 mm, > 6 mm),
90 Clark's level (< 4 , ≥ 4), presence of desmoplastic growth, site of primary tumour, number of
91 previous SCC, presence of immunosuppression, and budding index.

92 The 20 mm cut-off for horizontal tumour size was based on the TNM staging system (1).

93 Crude and adjusted hazard ratios were calculated with 95% CIs by using of the Cox
94 proportional-hazards model. Probabilities of nodal metastasis-free survival and overall
95 survival were estimated by Kaplan-Meier. The simultaneous prognostic effect of various
96 factors was determined in a multivariate analysis by using of the Cox proportional-hazard
97 regression model. The Kappa index was used to identify the correlation between the

98 presence of tumour buds and the other variables. We did not find any tumour with thickness
99 lower than 2 mm, and we dichotomized tumour thickness (≤ 6 mm or > 6 mm).

100 All reported p values are two-sided, values below 0.05 were considered statistically
101 significant.

102

103 RESULTS

104 Ninety-eight Caucasian patients were enrolled in the study. Seventy-six out of 98 patients
105 (Table 1) were men (78%). The metastatic tumor group means age in years was 79.1 ± 7.8
106 SD; median 81 [range 63-97]. The control group mean age was 78.6 ± 8.5 (SD; median 79
107 [range 52-96]. The median follow-up was 4.28 years, range 0.70 to 12, with total patient-
108 years of 432.5. Tumor budding was observed in 45 cases (46%) with a mean tumor bud
109 count of 5.9 ± 3.9 (range from 1 to 20 buds). High-intensity budding (≥ 5 tumor buds) was
110 observed in 20 tumors. As illustrated in Figure 1, tumor buds can be readily identified based
111 on standard H&E staining.

112 No relevant associations between the candidate predictors were noted except a moderate
113 correlation between tumour thickness and horizontal size (Spearman Rank Correlation
114 Coefficient $R=0.668$; $p<0.001$) based on the original scales (millimeters).

115 Twelve patients from the McSCC group suffered local recurrence prior to the regional
116 lymph-node metastasis. In five patients, nodal metastasis occurred within the first year after
117 resection. Two nodal metastases were detected immediately after the cSCC surgery.

118 On univariate analysis, increased tumour thickness, anatomic level, increased tumour size,
119 poor tumour differentiation, desmoplastic growth, pathologic staging, perineural invasion,

120 lymph-vascular invasion and presence of tumour buds were significantly associated with
121 nodal metastasis (Table 1).

122 Tumor buds were associated with tumor thickness, anatomic level, tumor horizontal size,
123 tumor differentiation, desmoplastic growth, pathologic staging and perineural invasion
124 (Table 2).

125 On the univariate model, the presence of buds has much effect on the risk of recurrence and
126 dead by the tumor. While 50% of patients without buds are still alive 5.23 years after
127 extirpation (95% CI of (4.48-8.56)), 50% of patients with buds had died before 2.95 (95%
128 CI of (2.07-4.78)) years and relapsed or died before 1.03 years (95% CI of (0.62-1.48)) with
129 a crude hazard ratio of 8.92 (95% CI of (4.39-18.1)). This effect is slightly modulated but it
130 was still important when it was adjusted by different potential confounders (Table 3). The
131 smallest HR was observed in the model 2 with a HR of 6.85 (95% CI of (3.03-15.4)).
132 Besides, although in a much less fashion, it shows itself as mortality risk factor with a crude
133 HR of 2.03 (95% CI of (1.26-3.28)). Again, this HR is modulated when we adjust by
134 possible confounders: smallest HR was observed in Model 3, just adjusting by tumor
135 thickness (HR=1.72 with a 95% CI of (1.05-2.83)). According to the last column, in all
136 models, all risk factors lose their meaning once metastasis occurs, that is, once a tumor
137 metastasizes, has the same risk of death regardless of their tumour buds.

138

139 As illustrated in Figure 2, upper-left, a striking difference in nodal metastasis-free survival
140 rates was observed between the budding and no-budding groups. At the third year, the
141 difference yields 65% (20% vs. 85% for the budding and no-budding groups, respectively
142 ($p < 0.001$)). The influence between below-five and greater or equal to five bud groups is
143 shown at lower-left figure.

144 Regarding to survival, Figure 2, upper-right, shows the difference for the survival
145 distribution: it was smaller than in the nodal metastasis-free survival, but remarkable. At
146 third year, a 50% in survival was observed (45% vs. 95% for the budding and no-budding
147 rates, respectively), then the difference decreases. The survival Kaplan-Meier curves for the
148 group below-five and greater or equal to five buds is shown at lower-right figure.

149

150 DISCUSSION

151

152 In this study, we assessed the role of buds as prognostic factor for lymphatic metastases in
153 cSCC. On the basis of data from a previous study (6) (13) we retrospectively analyzed the
154 risk factors associated with cSCC including the age, TNM staging, tumor site, tumor
155 thickness, tumor horizontal size, anatomic level, tumor differentiation, desmoplastic growth,
156 tumor site, multiple SCC, immunosuppression, perineural invasion, lymph-vascular invasion
157 as well as tumor budding.

158 Tumor budding, which resides ahead the invasive front, has recently been suggested as a
159 potential index of aggressiveness and poor prognosis for a number of cancer types (7-11, 14,
160 15). An important advantage of tumor budding-based index as prognostic indicator is the
161 simplicity and reproducible measurement of the budding. It is readily adaptable to routine
162 H&E staining based histopathological examination without the need for additional cost
163 demanding techniques. This feature is important and may have therapeutic implications for
164 the patients with SCC. In this study, in accordance with previous reports in other cancers a
165 good reproducibility for tumor budding evaluation was achieved based on the intra- and
166 inter-observer agreement studies ($\kappa=0.880$ or 0.818 and 0.717 , respectively) (8,14,16).
167 However, in a subset of poorly differentiated carcinomas, may be difficult to identify

168 isolated individual budding tumor cells among the surrounding tissue, which contains
169 inflammatory cells, cancer associated fibroblasts and other stromal cells. To highlight
170 budding status in such cases, an additional staining for pan-cytokeratin can be performed.
171 Nevertheless, a good reproducibility for tumour evaluation was achieved.

172

173 Nothing is known about the prognostic value of tumor budding in patients with cSCC. In
174 this study, we found that the 4-year survival was significantly reduced in patients exhibiting
175 tumor budding compared to patients without tumor budding. In the univariate analysis,
176 tumor budding has the highest hazard ratio for metastasis (8.92 [4.39-18.1]) after the
177 anatomic level (<4 versus ≥ 4) (10.6 [2.60-43.5] and, obviously, the pathologic staging
178 variables (26.9 [1.03-703.0]). In different multivariate analysis models, patients with buds
179 had 1.7 to 2.5 increased risk of death and 6.3 to 9.5 increased risk of nodal metastases. This
180 was also observed on studies in other solid tumors (e.g., larynx and esophageal cancer,
181 colorectal cancer), which also demonstrated strong associations of tumor budding with a
182 poor prognosis (10, 12, 17, 18). In agreement with other cancer studies, we observed
183 positive associations of high intensity tumor budding with lymph node metastasis and poor
184 prognosis.

185

186 We are well aware that there are several limitations in our report. First, there is potential bias
187 due to retrospective nature of our study. Second, the study is limited to head and neck cSCC.
188 Third, these findings might even be biased, because, in a University Hospital, the percentage
189 of poor prognostic tumour might be higher due to referral than in the daily ambulatory
190 practice. At this moment we want to point out that in our sample all the examined tumors are
191 thicker than 2 mm and all of them are from a primary excision. Surprisingly the ear and
192 immunosuppression did not bear a significantly increased risk of metastasis. In contrast with

193 other studies immunosuppression has not been associated with poor outcomes (6, 19, 20).
194 Haisma et al. (13) present a similar results about the lack of this association. This may be
195 because immunocompromised patients were compared to immunocompetent patients with a
196 large number of high-risk of head and neck cSCC. Another possible explanation is that only
197 a small fraction of our study population was immunosuppressed (12.2%). In several reviews
198 ear location have high rates of developing nodal metastasis (19) (20), but as well as Brantsch
199 et al. (6) we did not find the ear as a risk location for McSCC. The lack of statistical power
200 because of relatively low numbers of patients with these features may explain the failure to
201 detect as a risk factor that other studies have been found.

202

203 In conclusion, we addressed the independent prognostic relevance of tumor cell budding in
204 the cSCC. On the basis of this data, if this is confirmed in multicenter prospective studies,
205 we suggest to add the buds as criteria of high risk cSCC, at least in the head and neck cSCC.

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Abbreviations used: AJCC: American Joint Committee on cancer. cSCC: Cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma. McSCC: Nodal metastasis from cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma.

FIGURES:

Figure 1. (A) Tumor budding at the invasive front in cSCC (H&E, 20×). (B) Tumor budding with hyperchromatic nuclei in an H&E section (40×). Tumor buds were identified with arrowheads.

Figure 2. Upper-left, Kaplan-Meier estimates of nodal-free survival after resection of the primary cSCC. Upper-right, Kaplan-Meier estimates of survival after resection of the primary cSCC. Down-left, Kaplan-Meier curve for nodal-free survival after resection of the cSCC on the the group below-five and greater or equal to five buds. Down-right, Kaplan-Meier curve for survival after resection of the primary cSCC on the the group below-five and greater or equal to five buds.

TABLES:

Table 1: Patient demographic and baseline characteristics

	Total(N=98)	Non-MSCC(N=49)	MSCC (N=49)	p-Value	HR [95% CI]
Person-years	433	283	149	<0.001	
Sex, Male n (%)	76 (78)	36 (73)	49 (82)	0.468	1.34 [0.65-2.77]
Age, mean±sd	78.8±8.1	78.6±8.5	79.1±7.8	0.795	1.01 (0.97-1.04)
Tumour thickness, mm					
Mean±sd	9.02±6.6	5.5±3.9	12.5±6.9	<0.001	1.10 [1.07-1.14]
0-6mm	48 (49)	37 (75)	11 (22)	<0.001	1 (Ref)
> 6mm	50 (51)	12 (25)	38 (78)	<0.001	5.49 [2.79-10.8]
Anatomic Level					
<4	23 (24)	21 (43)	2 (4)	<0.001	1 (Ref)
≥4	75 (76)	28 (57)	47 (96)	<0.001	10.6 [2.56-43.5]
Tumour horizontal size					
Mean±sd, mm	22.9±14.2	16.8±8.3	28.9±16.3	<0.001	1.04 [1.03-1.06]
≤ 20mm	63 (64)	41 (84)	22 (45)	<0.001	1 (Ref)
> 20 mm	35 (36)	8 (16)	27 (55)	<0.001	3.87 [2.19-6.84]
Tumour differentiation					
Good/ Moderate	45 (96)	49 (100)	45 (92)	0.117	1 (Ref)
Poor	4 (4)	0 (0)	4 (8)	0.117	0.27 [0.10-0.79]
Desmoplastic growth					
No	84 (86)	47 (96)	37 (75)	0.007	1 (Ref)
Yes	14 (14)	2 (4)	12 (25)	0.007	3.01 [1.56-5.82]
Tumour site					
Ear	20 (20)	8 (16)	12 (25)	0.453	1 (Ref)
Not ear	78 (78)	41 (84)	37 (75)	0.453	0.78 [0.41-1.50]
Pathologic staging TNM					
pT1=1	12 (12)	12 (25)	0 (0)	<0.001	1 (Ref)
pT2=2	86 (88)	37 (75)	49 (100)	<0.001	26.9 [1.03-703]
Other SCC					
No=0	69 (70)	33 (67)	36 (74)	0.658	1 (Ref)
Yes=1	29 (30)	16 (33)	13 (26)	0.658	0.77 [0.41-1.46]
Immunosuppression					
Immunocompetent	87 (89)	44 (90)	43 (88)	1.000	1 (Ref)
Immunosuppressed	11 (11)	5 (10)	6 (12)	1.000	0.77 [0.41-1.45]
Perineural invasion					
Not identified	84 (86)	47 (96)	37 (75)	0.007	1 (Ref)
Present	14 (14)	2 (4)	12 (25)	0.007	3.64 [1.89-7.02]
Lymph-Vascular Invasion					
Not identified	95 (97)	49 (100)	46 (94)	0.242	1 (Ref)
Present	3 (3)	0 (0)	3 (6)	0.242	5.81 [1.70-19.9]
Tumour buds					
Not identified	53 (54)	43 (88)	10 (20)	<0.001	1 (Ref)
Present	45 (46)	6 (12)	39 (80)	<0.001	8.92 [4.39-18.1]
Tumour buds					
<5 or no buds	68 (69)	49 (100)	19 (39)	<0.001	1 (Ref)
≥5 buds	30 (31)	0 (0)	39 (61)	<0.001	5.58 [3.05-10.2]

Table 2: Correlations among tumor buds and clinical and histopathological features.

	Kappa Index	P-value
Tumour thickness	-0.106	0.001
Anatomic Level	-0.086	<0.001
Tumour horizontal size	-0.129	<0.001
Tumour differentiation	0.022	0.027
Desmoplastic growth	0.198	0.008
Pathologic staging	-0.038	0.030
Other cSCC	-0.056	0.559
Immunosuppression	0.085	0.211
Perineural invasion	0.155	0.039
Lymph-Vascular Invasion	0.051	0.233

Table 3: Univariate and multivariate models. **Model 1:** Adjusted by Age and Gender. **Model 2:** Adjusted by Age, Gender, and significant variables in the univariate analyses. **Model 3:** Using forward stepwise criteria based on Wald statistics: only Thickness was finally added to model. **+Brantsch:** tumour buds + Best Branch model variables (tumour thickness + tumour size + tumour site (ear; not ear) + Immunosuppression) ref (6). **+TNM:** tumour buds and TNM. Survival*: In survival analysis, the time-dependent variable metastasis was also included.

	Relapse-Free Time	Survival	Survival*
	HR [95% CI]	HR [95% CI]	HR [95% CI]
Univariate	8.92 [4.39-18.1]	2.03 [1.26-3.28]	0.91 [0.50-1.63]
Model 1	9.46 [4.56-19.6]	2.32 [1.40-3.86]	1.19 [0.65-2.19]
Model 2	6.85 [3.03-15.4]	2.45 [1.40-4.28]	1.11 [0.59-2.10]
Model 3	6.93 [3.30-14.5]	1.72 [1.05-2.83]	0.84 [0.46-1.53]
+Brantsch	7.15 [3.39-15.1]	1.86 [1.12-3.09]	0.99 [0.54-1.82]
+TNM	6.92[3.38-14.2]	2.11 [1.31-3.40]	0.95 [0.54-1.66]